

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)	27-09-2022		
Name/ID of person extracting data	MDL		
Author(s)	Rolving et al.		
Country of origin	Denmark		
Publication year	2015		
Title of article	Does a Preoperative Cognitive-Behavioral Intervention Affect Disability, Pain Behavior, Pain, and Return to Work the First Year After Lumbar Spinal Fusion Surgery?		
Title of journal	Spine		
Volume 40	Issue 9	Pages 593-600	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)	Scientific article		

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 593, 594
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	Patients with degenerative disc disease or spondylolisthesis undergoing LSF	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Abstract
Types of intervention	Preoperative cognitive-behavioral intervention	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 594
Types of comparison	Standard treatment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 594
Types of outcome	Pain, function disability/status, mental	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 594

measures	health, return to work				
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	To examine the effect of a preoperative CBT intervention in patients undergoing LSF. We hypothesized that the CBT intervention would outperform usual care without a preoperative CBT intervention in regard to disability, psychological variables, return to work, and back and leg pain.	p. 594
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	RCT	p. 594
Start date	October 2011	p. 594
End date	June 2013	p. 594
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear The study was approved by the Danish Protection Agency (2011-41-5899) and the Ethics Committee of Central Denmark Region (M-20110047).	p. 594

Participants

	Description	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
	<i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	
Setting (including location and social context)	Orthopedic Department of a university hospital and a general hospital	p. 594
Inclusion criteria	The inclusion criteria were (1) degenerative disease or spondylolisthesis grades 1 to 2; (2) fusion of a maximum of 3 adjacent vertebrae, (3) 18 to 64 years of age, and (4) competence in the Danish language.	p. 594
Exclusion criteria	Patients were excluded if surgery was scheduled to take place less than 4 weeks after inclusion, if they had a driving distance to the hospital of more than 80 km, or if they had psychiatric, inflammatory, or malignant diseases.	p. 594
Informed consent obtained	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unclear	

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	CBT Group	p. 594
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=59 (M:23, F:36) Mean age = 51.4	p. 596 table 1 p. 596 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Standard treatment and the following: Patients participated in six 3-hour group sessions (4 sessions preoperatively and 2 sessions postoperatively). The main topics covered were the interaction of cognition and pain perception, coping strategies, pacing principles, ergonomic directions, return to work, and details about the surgical procedure. Each treatment session was standardized, although some flexibility was allowed to meet the participants' needs. The team managing the intervention counted a psychologist, an occupational therapist, a physiotherapist, a social worker, a spine surgeon, and a previously operated patient. All health staff attended a 2-day training program to develop their basic CBT skills. A manual was handed out to all project staff to supplement the treatment sessions and to ensure uniformity of the sessions during the project period.	p. 594

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Control group / standard treatment	p. 594
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=31 (M:16, F:15) Mean age = 47.7	p. 596 table 1 p. 596 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Preoperative information about the upcoming operation and the anesthetic procedure, medication, and information about the postoperative rehabilitation and physical restrictions after surgery. Information was given by the operating surgeon, nurses, physiotherapists, and occupational therapists. The postoperative rehabilitation commenced 12 weeks after surgery, and it typically consisted of 8 weeks of supervised exercise either individually or in groups. It took place at rehabilitation centers or physiotherapy clinics in the patients' local area.	p. 594

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain (Back pain and leg pain)	p. 594
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Low Back Pain Rating Scale No difference	p. 594

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Function disability /status	p. 594
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) = primary outcome No difference	p. 594

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Mental health	p. 594
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Coping strategies Questionnaire; Fear avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire	p. 594

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Return to work	p. 594
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Danish Register for Evaluation of Marginalisation (DREAM)-data	p. 594

Follow up

Follow up	12 months	p. 597 table 2
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>Results: At 1-year follow-up, there was no statistically significant difference between the CBT group and the control group in Oswestry Disability Index score ($P = 0.082$). However, the CBT group had achieved a significant reduction of -15 points (-26; -4) already at 3 months (between group difference $P = 0.003$), and this reduction was maintained throughout the year. There were no differences between groups at 1-year follow-up with regard to any of the secondary outcomes.</p> <p>Conclusion: Participating in a preoperative CBT intervention in addition to usual care did not produce better outcomes at 1-year follow-up for patients undergoing LSF. Although the reduction in disability was achieved much faster in the CBT group, resulting in a significant difference between groups already 3 months after surgery, it did not translate into a faster return to work. Our findings support the need for further research into the use of targeted rehabilitation interventions among patients with elevated levels of catastrophizing and fear avoidance beliefs.</p> <p>Participation in a preoperative CBT intervention in addition to usual care did not produce better outcomes at 1-year follow-up for patients undergoing LSF. A reduction in disability was achieved much faster in the CBT group as reflected in a significant difference between the groups already 3 months after surgery, but it did not translate into faster resumption of work in the CBT group.</p>	<p>Abstract</p> <p>p. 599</p>

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>